

A Case Study of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing Modalities Used Successfully In The treatment of A Female Patient of Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA) With History of Sinus Tachycardia(ST)

¹Leelavathi Nayak, ²Venkata Satyanarayana Nanduri

¹*Yoga Prana Vidya Certified healer and trainer, Yoga Prana Vidya Ashram, Sri Ramana Trust, Thally-635118, Tamilnadu*

²*Consultant, Research & Publications, Yoga Prana Vidya Ashram, Sri Ramana Trust, Thally-635118, Tamilnadu*

Abstract

Introduction: Sinus tachycardia (ST) denotes a condition of heart beats of over 100 per minute, for which the usual causes are: strenuous exercise, a fever, fear, stress, anxiety, certain medications, anaemia, an overactive thyroid or damage from a heart attack. Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA) has symptoms similar to those of a stroke, but lasts only a few minutes and doesn't cause permanent damage. The usual causes of TIA are smoking, high blood pressure, obesity, high cholesterol, diabetes and excessive alcohol consumption. This paper presents a case of a female with TIA and past history of ST, treated by Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing techniques.

Method: This is a case study method analysing the diagnosis and treatment of a female patient, and the improvements noted from the application of YPV healing and results obtained from medical records and patient feedback.

Results: Within 2 days of YPV healing, her palpitation and BP returned to normal. Healings continued and day by day the patient was able to recover from her symptoms, and within a span of 20 days of healings, she got completely recovered from symptoms.

Conclusion: Yoga Prana Vidya system of healing and practice protocols cured the patient holistically to normalise from Sinus Tachycardia and Transient Ischemic attack together with other vital parameters. Further research may be conducted on appropriate sample to study the results on wider population.

Keywords: Sinus tachycardia (ST), Transient Ischemic attack (TIA), Yoga Prana Vidya System ®, YPV ®

I. Introduction

Sinus Tachycardia

Tachycardia is a condition that makes human heart beat more than 100 times per minute. There are three types of Tachycardia: (1) Supraventricular: This happens when the electrical signals in the organ's upper chambers misfire and cause the heart rate to speed up; (2) Ventricular: This is a rapid heart rate that starts in heart's lower chambers. It happens when the electrical signals in these chambers fire the wrong way, and (3) Sinus tachycardia (ST): This happens when heart's natural pacemaker sends out electrical signals faster than normal, causing the heart beat fast, but it beats the way it should. When it happens without clear reason, it is called Inappropriate Sinus Tachycardia (IST).[1].

Usual causes are: strenuous exercise, a fever, fear, stress, anxiety certain medications, and street drugs that can lead to sinus tachycardia. It can also be triggered by anaemia, an overactive thyroid or damage from a heart attack or heart failure.[1]

General symptoms are: rapid heartbeat, chest pain, breathing problems and feeling tired. May also be accompanied by dizziness or light-headedness. In rare cases, one may also faint because of a fast drop in blood pressure., pounding in the neck, sweating, tightness in the throat etc. [2]. The diagnosis is done by ECG (Electrocardiogram), that records the electrical activity in heart and helps the doctor search for things that don't look normal.

A detailed history is vital to decisions regarding the appropriate management of tachycardia. These include inquiring about precipitating factors (i.e., fever or exercise), recent medications, toxic exposures, drug or caffeine use, a history of illness, a history of heart disease or recent heart surgery, and family history. [2]. If left untreated, some forms of tachycardia can lead to serious health problems, including heart failure, stroke or sudden cardiac death. [2] Medical assessment can help pinpoint the cause and suggest ways to lower the heart rate, viz., lifestyle changes easing stress or taking medicine to lower a fever.

Unrecognized persistent sinus tachycardia due to a pathologic cause can result in myocardial ischemia, reduced ventricular filling time, resulting in decreased cardiac output, end-organ system failure, cardiomyopathy, cardiac arrest, and may result in death. [2].

Transient ischemic attack

A transient ischemic attack (TIA) is a temporary period of symptoms similar to those of a stroke. A TIA usually lasts only a few minutes and doesn't cause permanent damage. Often called a mini stroke, a TIA may be a warning sign.[3]. Transient ischemic attacks usually last a few minutes.

Most signs and symptoms disappear within an hour, though rarely symptoms may last up to 24 hours. The signs and symptoms of a TIA resemble those found early in a stroke and may include sudden onset of: weakness, numbness or paralysis in the face, arm or leg, typically on one side of the body, slurred or garbled speech or difficulty understanding others, blindness in one or both eyes or double vision and vertigo or loss of balance or coordination[4].

The causes generally are: smoking, high blood pressure (hypertension), obesity, high cholesterol levels, diabetes and excessive alcohol consumption. A type of irregular heartbeat called *atrial fibrillation* can also cause a TIA. It can lead to the formation of blood clots that escape from the heart and become lodged in the blood vessels supplying the brain.[5]. Treatments include: lifestyle changes, medicines and surgery.

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) System

Yoga Prana Vidya System is a no-touch and a no-drug energy healing modality which also works at a distance and can cure many physical or psychological problems. It is an integrated and a holistic system which promotes happiness and good health at physical, emotional and mental levels using rhythmic Yogic breathing, healing techniques, meditation and yoga. In the healing techniques, the healer removes the diseased, dirty or the used-up energy from the affected part or the affected chakrams of the patient and fills it up with fresh energy. The main advantage of using Yoga Prana Vidya healing techniques is, firstly that the patient need not be physically present in front of the healer as the healing can be done from a distance, and secondly, it can cure many psychological ailments too which are emotional or mental in nature.

Fig 1: Energy body of a healthy person Fig 2: Energy body of a sick person

Fig 3: Chakrams in the energy body Fig 4: GDV camera Images of energy body

The energy body, also known as *aura*, of a being surrounds the physical body, and it consists of an inner aura, an outer aura and health rays connecting these two. Figures 1 and 2 illustrate the energy body of a healthy person and sick person respectively. The energy body consists of chakrams (see figure 3) and “*nadis*” (meridians) for receiving and distributing the Pranic energy, also known as life force. Figure 4 shows the pictures of human aura taken using GDV (Gas Discharge Visualisation) camera before and after healing and correlates with images in figures 1 and 2 respectively. Yoga Prana Vidya system consists of self-practice modules such as physical exercises, Rhythmic yogic breathing, and meditation practices such as forgiveness sadhana and Planetary Peace Meditation. The healing process consists of several basic and advanced techniques of cleansing the chakrams and affected parts and energizing the same for desired results.

Published literature of over 40 articles shows that, by using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing techniques, many cases have been successfully treated such as, some difficult medical cases [6], Diabetes management & control [7], removing arterial block in heart without surgery [8], vision improvements for participants of an Eye Camp [9], improvements in holistic wellbeing and immunity of participants in a one-month YPV intensive programme [10], Role of Yoga Prana Vidya in first aid and emergency [11], improvements of health and immunity of senior citizens [12], speedy recovery of COVID patients [13], treatment of hypothyroidism [14], Lowering academic

anxiety and enhancing academic performance of high school children [15], saving life of a snake-bitten human female [16], improvements in the cognitive abilities and social behaviour of mentally challenged children [17], managing the pain and side effects of a Hodgkin Lymphoma patient undergoing chemotherapy [18], healing treatment of a female patient suffering from kneecap dislocation [19]. A review of published literature shows some experimental studies also conducted with successful outcomes such as improvements in the wellbeing of prisoners [20], and significant reduction in anxiety and depression in corporate employees [21].

This paper presents a case of a 51 years aged female patient who had experienced symptoms of Sinus Tachycardia (ST) (previously in 2017 when she was 46 years aged), and later on experienced a Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA) in 2020, was successfully healed by YPV healer on both occasions.

II. Method

This is a case study method analysing the diagnosis and treatment of a female patient, and the improvements noted from the application of YPV healing and results obtained from medical records and patient feedback.

III. Case Report

The patient was 46 years aged at the time of episode 1, female home maker, resident of Mangalore in Karnataka.

Episode 1: Diagnosed sinus tachycardia (2017)

In 2017 the patient observed symptoms, like when she bends her head or see the mobile, she was feeling some kind of tightness in the tongue, high palpitation and there was a pain in neck towards right side. Besides that, she felt tightness in the chest, tiredness, breathlessness while walking and while climbing stairs. Her doctor did an ECG test and found ECG was normal, but showing to have slight increase in heart rate, and her BP was also somewhat on the higher side. The doctor advised that there was no need to take any medications at that stage, but advised her to do some exercises daily including walking to reduce weight.

Figure 1 ECG taken in 2017: diagnosed Sinus Tachycardia

One of her friends advised her to consult a YPV Healer who advised her to do some breathing exercises and to do forgiveness sadhana, and further advised that any of the physical, emotional and mental problems can be treated through healings. The patient started doing breathing exercises and forgiveness technique daily. Gradually her problems started reducing and a week later, she felt much better. The symptoms almost disappeared and she continued the breathing exercises and forgiveness sadhana techniques. After nearly a month, healings were stopped. Much later the patient came back with new reports with all tests, just to make sure everything was ok. These test reports showed results were all normal except that triglycerides were little high (figure 2 and Annexure 1).

Fig 2 ECG showing normal rhythm and short PR interval (25-01-2021)

Episode 2: Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA) (March 2021)

Later in 2021 March, again she developed the symptoms like palpitation, heaviness in the chest, sometimes tightness in the tongue and slurred speech and pain in the neck. Since the symptoms caused worry, she went to a neurologist. Based on the symptoms, he considered it as Ischemic episode, suggested to go for an MRI Brain scan to assess the condition and the doctor found the MRI scan to be normal (Annexure 2) and it was diagnosed as TIA. Gradually her symptoms decreased somewhat, but not completely. Since the Covid 19 pandemic was severe at that time, she followed up with the visit to doctor only in November 2021. Because her symptoms were still persistent, the doctor advised her to do Echo test also. Following the tests, the doctor found the EchoDoppler reports to be normal (Annexure 3). The doctor prescribed to take Ecosprin AV tablet to prevent blood clotting and stroke based on the symptoms.

At that stage (in November 2021), the patient contacted the YPV healer again and requested for healings. The healer started with Healings, while simultaneously suggested to her to regularly and sincerely practice exercises and sadhanas for better and quick results, viz, (1) Rhythmic yogic breathing, (2) forgiveness Sadhana together with fruit diet and saltless food to restore tonormalcy. YPV level 2 and 3 healings were given to the patient daily for 3 weeks to reduce stress and physical conditions. Heart, lungs, spleen, throat, brain, arms and legs were treated by level 2 techniques using color energies.

Within 2 days of healing, her palpitation and BP returned to normal. Healings continued and day by day she was able to recover from her symptoms, and within a span of 20 days of healings, she got completely recovered from symptoms. The patient was very happy and satisfied with the holistic approach of YPV healing techniques and promised to continue the YPV guidelines given.

Patient feedback

Episode 1: Diagnosed sinus tachycardia

“Myself xxx (name withheld), 51 years old female, giving information that, in 2017 October, I had developed palpitation, heaviness in the chest, tiredness, breathlessness while walking and while climbing stairs, I went to a doctor, he did a ECG test and told me that you have sinus tachycardia and increase in heart rate, and your BP is also little higher side. He told me that no need to take any medications now, but he advised me to do some exercises and go for walking daily and to reduce weight.

One of my friends advised me to consult a YPV Healer, then she took me to a healer. The healer advised me to do some breathing exercises and to do forgiveness technique, and she also told me that any of the physical, emotional and mental problems can be treated through healings. She started doing the healings. I also started doing breathing exercises and forgiveness technique daily as suggested. Gradually my problems started reducing and approximately in one week I felt much better, almost the symptoms disappeared. I continued the breathing exercises and forgiveness technique. YPV Healings were stopped after one month. Later report had also shown that there was no ST condition

Episode 2: Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA)

“Later in 2021 march, again I developed the symptoms like palpitation, heaviness in the chest, sometimes tightness in the tongue and slurred speech and pain in the neck. Since the symptoms were worried to me, I went to a neurologist. Considering it as Ischemic episode he advised me to do an MRI Brain scan, and the doctor told me that, The MRI scan is normal and that it was a case of TIA. Gradually my symptoms decreased a little but not completely. Since the Covid 19 was present I went for follow up only in November 2021, and since my symptoms still persistent, doctor advised me to do Echo test. The doctor told me that Doppler reports are normal, and he advised me to take Ecosprin AV tablet to prevent stroke based on the symptoms.

I again consulted to the YPV Healer in November 2021 and I took further healings for about 3 weeks for my problems. The healer also advised me to continue the breathing exercises and forgiveness technique regularly, and she also advised me to take salt restricted diet and to eat plenty of fruits and vegetables.

Gradually my problems decreased and disappeared. Now I don't have any such kind of symptoms and my BP also is normal at 110/70 and HR around 80 bpm. I did not go to the doctor again for further treatment. I am presently not taking any medications. I am following all the YPV guidelines given and maintaining my health.”

Discussion

The current concept of TIA characterizes an ischemic episode in which symptoms are transient and not associated with brain injury. But recent evidence suggests that such episodes do not occur or are vanishingly rare and that brain injury almost always occurs during these events. Accordingly, it is time to re-evaluate the conceptual soundness and utility of the term TIA. [5]. Literature shows that in the past a case of successful healing treatment of a brain stroke of a female patient using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) system was reported [22]. It is therefore observed that YPV can safely be applied to diseases such as ST and TIA successfully.

Conclusions

Yoga Prana Vidya system of healing and practice protocols cured the patient holistically to normalise from Sinus Tachycardia and Transient Ischemic attack together with other vital parameters. Further research may be conducted on appropriate sample to study the results on wider population.

Acknowledgements

Our grateful thanks are to Sri Ramana Trust for permission given to use their copyright terms Yoga Prana Vidya ®, and YPV ®, and also to the patient and her family for sharing the case details with feedback.

References

- [1.] James Beckerman. Tachycardia, December 04, 2019. Available <https://www.webmd.com/heart-disease/atrial-fibrillation/what-are-the-types-of-tachycardia>
- [2.] Healthline. Sinus tachycardia. Available <https://www.healthline.com/health/sinus-tachycardia>, 2022
- [3.] Mayo clinic. Transient Ischemic Attack. Available <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/transient-ischemic-attack/symptoms-causes/syc-20355679>
- [4.] NHS. Transient Ischemic Attack. Available <https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/transient-ischaemic-attack-tia/>
- [5.] Easton JD, Johnston SC. Time to Retire the Concept of Transient Ischemic Attack. *JAMA*. 2022;327(9):813–814. doi:10.1001/jama.2022.0300
- [6.] Neravetla J, Nanduri VS. A study into the successful treatment of some difficult Medical cases using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing System as alternative medicine. *Int J Sci Eng Res*, 2019, 10 (7):882-8877
- [7.] Rajagopal AH, Ramya A, Nanduri, VS. Diabetes Management and Control Using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing System, *Journal of Biology and Life Science* ISSN 2157-6076, 2019, Vol. 10, No. 2
- [8.] Ramya A, Nanduri VS. Cardiac Case Study: Successful Healing Treatment of a 48-Year-Old Male with Block in Heart, Using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing System. *Saudi J Nurs Health Care*, Nov 2019; 2(11): 353-356. <https://www.yogapranavidya.com/about-ypv-research/publications/successful-healing-treatment-of-a-48-year-old-male-with-block-in-heart-using-ypv/>
- [9.] Nanduri VS, Chaitra N. How the participants of a Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Eye Camp experienced vision improvements: A Case study. *The Journal of Community Health Management*. (2019) 6(4): 139-146. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.18231/j.jchm.2019.028>
- [10.] Neravetla J, Nanduri VS. A study of the effects of Yoga Prana Vidya one-month intensive residential programme for participants on their physical health, psychological well-being and improved immunity. *International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews (IJRAR)*, 7(2), 18-27.
- [11.] Neravetla J, Nanduri VS. Role of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing Techniques in Emergency and First Aid: A Summary of Case Reports. *International Journal of Medical Science and Health Research*. 4(3), 133-146
- [12.] Nanduri VS. Effectiveness of Yoga Prana Vidya practice protocols for health improvements and boosting immunity of seniors – A review. *J.Bio.Innov* 9(4), pp: 583-588, 2020 |ISSN 2277-8330 (Electronic)
- [13.] Nanduri VS, Karnani V. Successful and speedy recovery of COVID patients using Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Healing. *Covid-19 2020*; 1(4):78-82 Doi: <http://doi.org/10.18231/j.covid.2020.005>
- [14.] Revathi R, Janani N, Nanduri, VS. Successful healing treatment of Hypothyroidism using Integrated Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing approach as complementary medicine: Case reports. *J Prev Med Holistic Health* 2020;6(1):1-7.
- [15.] Ramya A, Kraleti P, Gopal KVT, Nanduri, VS. Efficacy of Planetary Peace Meditation (PPM) of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) System in Enhancing Academic Performance of High School Children: A Case study. *Indian Journal of Psychology and Education*, 10 (2), July 2020, 59-64. ISSN -2231-1432

- [16.] Ramya A, Ashwin V, Divya D, Nanduri VS. Serious snake bite case: successful treatment using yoga prana vidya (YPV) healing system. 2021; 5 (01):101-110 <http://dx.doi.org/10.51505/ijmsdr.2021.5111>
DOI: 10.51505/ijmsdr.2021.5111
- [17.] Rajkumari K, Bembalkar S, Nanduri VS. A Pilot Study of the Effects of Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) protocols on social behaviour, cognitive abilities and IQ of mentally challenged children, Pediatric Review – International Journal of Pediatric Research-2021 Volume 8 Number 1 (January-February-2021):7-15 Available From <https://pediatrics.medresearch.in/index.php/ijpr/article/view/653>
- [18.] Jain V, Bindal S, Bhatia PK, Nanduri VS. Managing pain and side effects of a Hodgkin lymphoma female patient undergoing Chemotherapy using Yoga Prana Vidya System as complementary medicine: A case report. International Journal of Medical Sciences and Academic Research, v. 2, n. 05, 30 Oct. 2021.
- [19.] Dholakia M, Tandon I, Dholakia D, Nanduri, VS. "Successful Healing Treatment of Kneecap (Patellar) Dislocation of a Teen Female Patient Using Yoga Prana Vidya System Protocols without Surgery: A Case Report". Acta Scientific Women's Health 3.11 (2021): 15-20.
- [20.] Nanduri VS, Revathi R. Effects of Yoga Prana Vidya intervention on psychological wellbeing and criminal attitude of under-trial prisoners. Ind J Psychiatric Social Work. 2020; 11(2).Epub.1-9 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.29120/ijpsw.2020.v11.i2.232>
- [21.] Nanduri VS. A Study on the Effects of Yoga Prana Vidya System (YPV) Intervention at workplace for Corporate Employees and Executives to alleviate Anxiety, Depression and Burnout; and participants' perceptions and experiences of the YPV Intervention. International Journal of Indian Psychology, 2020;8(3), 374-390. DIP:18.01.047/20200803, DOI:10.25215/0803.047
- [22.] Kataria R, Nanduri VS. Successful healing treatment of a brain stroke case of a female patient using yoga prana vidya system- a case report. JBioInnov10(6), pp: 1533-1540, 2021 |ISSN 2277-8330. <https://doi.org/10.46344/JBINO.2021.v10i06.06>

Annexures

BIOCHEMISTRY			
TEST	RESULT	UNIT	REFERENCE
HDL- CHOLESTEROL Method: Direct Enzymatic	47.6	mg/dl	[40.0-60.0]
SERUM CREATININE Method: Jaffe Colorimetric	0.60	mg/dl	[0.40-1.40]
THYROID PROFILE, Serum			
T3 - Triiodothyronine Method: ECLIA	0.920	ng/dl	[0.800-2.000]
T4 - Thyroxine Method: ECLIA	7.25	ugm/dl	[5.10-14.10]
Thyroid Stimulating Hormone Method: ECLIA	2.060	uIU/ml	[0.270-4.200]
Note : TSH levels are subject to circadian variation, reaching peak levels between 2-4.a.m.and at a minimum between 6-10 pm.Factors such as change of seasons hormonal fluctuations, Ca or Fe supplements, high fibre diet, stress and illness affect TSH results. * References ranges recommended by the American Thyroid Association 1) Thyroid. 2011 Oct;21(10):1081-125.PMID .21787128 2) http://www.thyroid-info.com/articles/tsh-fluctuating.html			
TRIGLYCERIDES Method: GPO/PAP	201.0 #	mg/dl	[0.0-150.0] High: 200 - 499 Very high: >500 Borderline high:151-199

Annexure 1 Bio-chemistry results (25-01-2021)

MRI STUDY OF BRAIN + MRA

- Bilateral cerebral and cerebellar hemispheres show no areas of altered intensities.
- Bilateral thalami, internal capsule and basal ganglia appear normal.
- No areas of diffusion restriction.
- Optic nerve, optic chiasm, pituitary gland, infundibulum and hypothalamic regions are normal.
- Orbits appear normal. Bilateral extra ocular muscles appear normal.
- Bilateral lateral and 3rd ventricles are normal.
- 4th ventricle appears normal.
- Sylvian fissures, basal cisterns and cortical sulci appear normal.
- Corpus callosum is normal.
- Brain stem appears normal.
- Bilateral CP angle cisterns appear normal.
- Visualized cranial nerves appear normal.
- Internal auditory canals appear normal.
- **Mucosal thickening in bilateral maxillary sinuses(left>right) and right ethmoidal sinuses- sinusitis**

MRA:

- No abnormality in cerebral MR angiogram.
- Hypoplastic bilateral PCom arteries.

IMPRESSION:

- > No areas of altered signal intensities in the neuroparenchyma

Annexure 2 MRI brain Scan 07-03-2021

14. LV WALL MOTION ABNORMALITIES (SPECIFY AREA):

LEVEL	SEGMENT				Vs. Inf.
	Vs. Ant.	Ant.	Lat.	Inf.	
BASAL	1	2	3	4	5
MID	6	7	8	9	10
APICAL	11	12	13	14	15
RV	16				

WALL MOTION SCORE
 I - NORMAL
 II - HYPOKINESIA
 III - AKINESIA
 IV - DYSKINESIA
 V - ANEURYSM

LVMW SCORE INDEX
 ABNORMAL SEPTUM
 NORMAL SEPTUM

15. COLOUR FLOW MAPPING (2D IMAGES)
 Long Axis View; 4 Chamber View; Subcostal View; Short Axis View

- Normal chamber size
- No RWMA
- Normal valves
- Good LV systolic function (Ef = 65%)

FINAL CONCLUSIONS:

- No AS / AR
- No MS / MR
- No TR / PAF
- IVC (N), collapse (+)
- No clot / pericardial effusion: ?

Suboptimal Echo window.

CONSULTANT CARDIOLOGIST
 Dr. RAJESH BHAT U.
 (M.D., F.I.C.C., F.C.C.P., F.C.C.I.)
 Senior Consultant Cardiologist
 Senior Sp. in Echocardiography
 K.J. Somaiya Institute of Postgraduate Medical Education

Annexure 3 Cardiac report 15-11-2021 - Doppler study